

CO-OCCURRENCE ANALYSIS OF *GRAPHOSOMA ITALICUM ITALICUM* SPECIES AND THEIR AFFINITY TO SELECTED PLANT SPECIES IN ARMENIA**Tsaturyan A.,**

PhD student

“Hydrometeorology and Monitoring Center” SNCO of the Ministry of Environment
Yerevan, Armenia**Vardanyan E.,**

PhD

“Hydrometeorology and Monitoring Center” SNCO of the Ministry of Environment
Yerevan, Armenia**Sargsyan M.**

MS

“Hydrometeorology and Monitoring Center” SNCO of the Ministry of Environment
Yerevan, Armenia**Abstract**

Graphosoma italicum italicum (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) is a phytophagous true bug widely distributed across the Western Palearctic and frequently associated with Apiaceae plants. In Armenia, its ecological relationships remain understudied despite increasing availability of biodiversity records. This study investigates the spatial co-occurrence between *G. italicum italicum* and selected Apiaceae genera (*Anthriscus*, *Heracleum*, *Daucus*, *Prangos*, *Falcaria*) across Armenia, using a combined dataset of field surveys (2023–2025) and open-access records. Data was processed through a uniform 3.5×3.5 km spatial grid, and species overlap was quantified using the Jaccard Similarity Index. A total of 50 insect records and over 100 plant observations were analyzed. The highest co-occurrence was found with *Anthriscus* ($J = 0.2$), followed by *Heracleum* ($J = 0.1$), while *Falcaria* showed the weakest spatial association ($J = 0.07$). Results indicate moderate but ecologically meaningful spatial overlap, suggesting potential host preference or shared habitat affinity. This study provides a foundation for future research on plant–insect interactions and spatial ecology in the South Caucasus.

Keywords: biodiversity, monitoring, distribution, Jaccard index.

Introduction

Graphosoma italicum italicum (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae), commonly known as the striped shield bug, is a phytophagous true bug widely distributed across the Western Palearctic region. In Armenia, it is frequently observed in dry open habitats, including steppe, subalpine meadows, and semi-disturbed grasslands [1]. The species is visually distinctive, relatively easy to detect, exhibiting a strong and consistent association with members of the Apiaceae family, particularly during their flowering period [2, 3].

Plant–insect associations, particularly those involving phytophagous Hemiptera, are often driven by host plant availability, phenology, and shared habitat preferences [3]. While feeding relationships and basic host plant data are available for many Pentatomidae species, quantitative analyses of their co-occurrence with plant taxa in specific regional contexts remain limited. For Armenia, such relationships have been largely understudied, despite the country's ecological diversity and the increasing availability of georeferenced species occurrence data.

This study focuses on the spatial co-occurrence patterns between *Graphosoma italicum italicum* and several vascular plant taxa in Armenia. Specifically, we analyze overlap with commonly associated plant genera from the Apiaceae family which have been repeatedly documented as host or activity plants for this species in the literature and regional observations. Using presence-only occurrence records and spatial grid analysis, we apply the Jaccard similarity index to quantify co-occurrence patterns between this insect species and selected plant taxa across the Armenian landscape [4].

The primary objective is to determine whether significant spatial overlap exists between *G. italicum italicum* and the presumed host plant taxa, and to what extent such overlap reflects shared habitat affinities or potential plant specificity. The results aim to contribute to a better understanding of the ecological relationships between phytophagous Hemiptera and their associated flora in the South Caucasus, offering a baseline for future work on species interactions and biogeographic structure in the region. This will contribute using Jaccard index calculation method especially for environmental indicator species.

Materials and methods**Species overview***Graphosoma italicum italicum*

The focal insect species for this study is *Graphosoma italicum italicum* (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae), a phytophagous true bug primarily associated with members of the Apiaceae family [1]. To evaluate potential co-occurrence patterns, three commonly recorded plant genera were selected based on literature and field observations: *Ferula*, *Heracleum*, and *Daucus* (Apiaceae). These genera are widespread across Armenia and represent typical floral components of the habitats where *G. italicum* is frequently observed.

Target Plants /Apiaceae

All genera from the family Apiaceae were selected based on literature and field observations for known associations with *G. italicum italicum*. These taxa represent widespread and ecologically significant components of Armenia's dry steppe and meadow flora, and have been repeatedly documented as feeding and reproductive hosts for *G. italicum* [5, 6].

Data collection

Field surveys were conducted across various ecological regions of Armenia between 2023 and 2025 by the Hydrometeorology and monitoring center. Data collection combined two complementary approaches:

Structured Transects: Standardized linear transects were established across grassland and steppe habitats, primarily during peak activity months (June–August). Each transect was walked, and all encountered individuals of *G. italicum italicum* and selected plant species were recorded.

Random Observations: Outside of structured transects, random observations were made during broader biodiversity surveys. In this case quantitative data were not recorded.

All field data were georeferenced using the **Survey123 mobile app** (ESRI), which allowed for standardized recording of coordinates (with <10 m GPS accuracy), species names, and in some cases, number of individuals.

Data Integration and Processing

In addition, primary field data collected by the Biodiversity monitoring group from Hydrometeorology and monitoring center, and verified open-source records from platforms such as GBIF and iNaturalist were integrated. Only observations with coordinate uncertainty below 500 meters and recorded after the year 2010 were included.

All data were processed in ArcGIS online and projected to the WGS 84 / UTM Zone 38N coordinate system. Two datasets were created:

- Occurrences of *Graphosoma italicum italicum*
- Occurrences of *Apiaceae* plant species

Plant species located within a **2 km radius** of insect records were extracted for further analysis. Duplicate records, urban outliers, and invalid coordinates (e.g., water bodies) were removed.

7/3/2025

- ◆ *Graphosoma italicum italicum* World_Hillshade
- *Apiaceae*

1:2,311,162
0 15 30 60 mi
0 20 40 80 km
Sources: Esri, TomTom, Garmin, FAO, NOAA, USGS, OpenStreetMap contributors, and the GIS User Community. Esri, USGS

Map 1: Raw data distribution

Correlation analysis

To assess potential associations between plant abundance and insect occurrence, a correlation analysis was conducted. All plant species located within a 2 km radius of each *Graphosoma italicum italicum* observation point were included in the analysis. The relationship between the number of insect individuals and the abundance of surrounding plant species was examined to evaluate whether higher plant presence corresponded to greater insect activity. This approach allowed us to explore local-scale spatial correlations and identify potential patterns of habitat preference or host plant affinity.

Distribution analysis

Distribution maps for *G. italicum italicum* and associated plant species were created using ArcGIS Online. Overlay analysis was used to identify co-occurrence zones.

The final dataset was overlaid on a uniform 3.5×3.5 km grid, which has been created using GIS Pro and species presence–absence matrices were generated in ArcGIS Online.

Co-occurrence analysis

We assessed spatial overlap between *Graphosoma italicum italicum* and each plant genus using the Jaccard Similarity Index (J):

$$J(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}$$

Where:

- A = Number of cells with *G. italicum italicum*
- B = Number of cells with the plant taxon
- A ∩ B = Number of cells with both

Higher J values indicate stronger spatial association [7]. All calculations were performed in **Python** using the **vegan** and **pandas** libraries.

Results and Discussion

As a result of correlation analysis, plant genres which have the highest correlation to insect quantitative

values were as follows: *Anthriscus*, *Heracleum*, *Daucus*, *Prangos*, and *Falcaria*.

A total of **50 occurrence records** of *Graphosoma italicum italicum* and more than **250 records** of plant taxa from the genera *Anthriscus*, *Heracleum*, *Daucus*, *Prangos*, and *Falcaria* were analyzed. After cleaning and spatial filtering, **grid cells** (3.5 × 3.5 km) were retained for final co-occurrence analysis.

Graphosoma italicum italicum was recorded in **35 grid cells**, mostly concentrated in dry steppe and sub-alpine meadow regions

Jaccard Co-occurrence Results

Plant genres which had higher correlation were mapped and the number of occurrence and co-occurrence with *G. Italicum* grid cells were counted.

Map 2. Prangos x G. Italicum Italicum and Heracleum x G. Italicum Italicum observation data

Map 3. Dauxus x G. Italicum Italicum and Falcaria x G. Italicum Italicum observation data

G. italicum x Anthriscus

Map 4. *Anthriscus x G. Italicum Italicum* observation data

The values were calculated based on the map's grid cells and were presented in the table below.

Table 1.

Jaccard Similarity index values and Occurrence Metrics for *Graphosoma italicum italicum* and Apiaceae Family

Plant Genus	Grid Cells (Co-occurrence)	Grid Cells (Plant)	Total Observations	Jaccard Index
<i>Anthriscus</i>	11	27	56	0.2
<i>Heracleum</i>	9	59	112	0.1
<i>Daucus</i>	8	50	84	0.09
<i>Prangos</i>	7	52	104	0.08
<i>Falcaria</i>	4	23	34	0.07

The strongest spatial association was observed with *Anthriscus* ($J = 0.2$), followed by *Heracleum* ($J = 0.1$). *Falcaria* showed the weakest co-occurrence pattern, likely due to its lower regional abundance or differing microhabitat requirements.

Conclusion

This study provides the first spatially explicit assessment of co-occurrence patterns between *Graphosoma italicum italicum* and selected Apiaceae plant genera in Armenia. Using georeferenced field data and open-source records, we quantified spatial overlap across multiple plant taxa and revealed varying degrees of association. Among the analyzed genera,

Anthriscus and *Heracleum* exhibited the highest co-occurrence values with *G. italicum italicum*, while *Falcaria* showed the lowest.

The results suggest a non-random spatial relationship between the insect and specific plant groups, likely reflecting ecological preferences tied to feeding and reproductive behavior. These findings contribute to our understanding of plant–insect spatial interactions in the South Caucasus and provide a foundation for future studies on habitat specificity, ecological networks, and insect phenology in Armenia's dry grassland systems.

Further research incorporating seasonal variation, abundance data, and finer-scale vegetation surveys

would enhance the resolution of these patterns and clarify the ecological roles of both the insect and its host plants within Armenian landscapes.

References

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